

More on the Application of the 2x2 Dirac Type Matrix Equation to Statistical Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell July 18, 2018

In a series of notes [2]-[9], a 2x2 matrix equation, linear in energy, was obtained from Einstein's energy momentum equation $E^2=p^2+m^2$ (1) which reproduced Schrodinger zitterbewegung [1]. In [22], [24], a similar equation was applied to the case of a gas with two allowable energy levels and to a gas in a potential field, the goal being to obtain zitterbewegung results in statistical mechanics. The starting point for applying the 2x2 matrix equation to statistical mechanics was the fact that the 2x2 matrix approach yields an eigenvector which is the square root of two probabilities which sum to one. In this note, we wish to see if we can extend ideas further. First, we wish to see if there are stronger reasons for applying the 2x2 matrix approach to statistical mechanics, and second, we wish to find further analogies between the approach and statistical mechanics. We consider relationships between physical constraint equations and the 2x2 matrix approach., We also consider functions analogous to the rest mass and energy in the statistical case, where the analogous energy also represents the frequency in zitterbewegung.

2x2 Matrix Approach

In [2]-[9], it was shown that one could convert the energy momentum equation (1) into:

$$\begin{pmatrix} |p & m| \\ |m & -p| \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} |\sqrt{1+v}| \\ |\sqrt{1-v}| \end{pmatrix} = E \begin{pmatrix} |\sqrt{1+v}| \\ |\sqrt{1+v}| \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Here p is the momentum, m the rest mass, E the energy and v the one dimensional velocity. It should be noted that the eigenvector represents the square root of the probabilities for a particle to move forward and backwards with speed c as it moves to the right overall with speed v. Knuth has also developed a similar model. [18]

It should be noted that the portion of the "energy" matrix containing "p" namely:

$$\begin{pmatrix} |p & 0| \\ |0 & -p| \end{pmatrix} \text{ is essentially the same as a constraint matrix } V = \begin{pmatrix} |1 & 0| \\ |0 & -1| \end{pmatrix}$$

Where V is the velocity operator such that its expectation with the eigenvector gives v.

Now, one can divide (2) by E to obtain the following result:

$$\begin{pmatrix} |\cos(a) & \sin(a)| \\ |\sin(a) & -\cos(a)| \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} |\cos(a/2)| \\ |\sin(a/2)| \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} |\cos(a/2)| \\ |\sin(a/2)| \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The eigenvector is normalized in this case. It is important to note that the identity matrix together with the energy matrix in (3) can convert any 2 vector into the eigenvector. Thus, $\exp(iHt)$ appears to be an evolution operator. One should note, however, that H carries the magnitude of E , as in (2). One may ask if this magnitude is important. It seems to be as:

$$[V,H] = dV/dt = -2m \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$$

Thus, the acceleration operator depends explicitly on the magnitude $2m$, so the exact form of the energy matrix in (2) is important even though the matrix in (3) has many interesting properties.

Statistical Mechanics Case

In the case of statistical mechanics, or at least the two examples considered in [22] and [24], there is no equation like the energy momentum equation (1). In previous notes, properties of the matrix in (3) were applied to the statistical case to see if they could provide interesting information. Here, we wish to see if we can obtain a matrix similar to that of (2). Let us restrict ourselves to infinitesimal cases as they are related to constraints.

Case of a Potential field $U(r)$

In this case, the problem can readily be expressed in infinitesimal terms because one can consider a small box of gas at r supported by the difference in pressures at $r+b$ and $r-b$ where b is infinitesimal. The pressure is assumed to be proportional to the density (ideal gas law). One can then write a pressure balance constraint equation as is often done in statistical mechanics textbooks:

Delta Pressure (P) is proportional to m of box times $-\text{grad } U(r)$ where $U(r)$ is the potential.

With ΔP proportional to $T[\text{density}(r+b) - \text{density}(r-b)] N/\text{Vol}$ where N is the total number of particles in a volume Vol .

If one examines the matrix in (3), then $\cos(a) = \cos(a/2)^2 - \sin(a/2)^2$
 Here $\cos(a/2)^2$ is the probability density at $r+b$ and $\sin(a/2)^2$ the probability density at $r-b$. Thus, the diagonal terms of the matrix are already participating in a constraint equation, just as in the regular Dirac 2x2 matrix case. Let us examine this constraint equation in more detail. This is obtained by multiplying the first row of the matrix in (3) by the eigenvector and setting it equal to the eigenvalue 1 times the first element of the eigenvector.

$$[\cos(a/2)^2 - \sin(a/2)^2] \cos(a/2) - 2 \cos(a/2)\sin(a/2) \sin(a/2) = \cos(a/2)$$

One may divide by $\cos(a/2)$ and note that $\cos(a/2)$ is equal to $C \exp(-U(r+b)/2T)$ and $\sin(a/2)$ to $C \exp(-U(r-b)/2T)$ where $C = \sqrt{\exp(-U(r+b)/T) + \exp(-U(r-b)/T)}$. Then:

$$[\Delta \text{ Pressure}]/[T N/\text{Vol}] - 2 \exp(-U(r)/T) \exp(-b \, dU/dr/T) = 1$$

The first term is infinitesimal so keeping only infinitesimal terms yields:

$$[\Delta \text{ pressure}] = 2 \exp(-U(r)/T) (-b \, dU/dr) \quad (4)$$

Here $\exp(-U(r)/T)$ is proportional to the mass of the box supported by the difference in pressures. Thus, one seems to recover a constraint equation by using the 2x2 matrix approach. One can try to push the analogy further. One can note that the analogous rest mass m appearing in (2) seems to be equal to $2N/\text{Vol} \exp(-U(r)/T)/C_1$ where C_1 is a normalization constant..

In the 2x2 case, the constraint value is v the velocity which is related to the energy by: $E = m/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ where c , the speed of light has been set to 1. In the statistical mechanics case, the constraint is:

Density 1 - density 2 = $2 \exp(-U(r)/T)(-b \, dU/dr / T)$ Let us call the RHS w which is tiny. Then an analogous expression for energy for the statistical case could be:

$m/\sqrt{1-w^2}$ With w tiny, one can perform a “nonrelativistic analogous expansion” to obtain:

(5) Energy analogy = $m + m \cdot 5 w^2$ with $m = N/\text{Vol} \exp(-U(r)/T)/C_1$ where C_1 is a normalization constant. We have not included the factor of 2 because it might associated with the length of the box $2b$.

Thus, a statistical gas in a potential field seems to have a kind of “kinetic energy” term $m \cdot 5 w^2$ which varies as one moves through the potential.

It is good to compare this analogous energy expression with:

$$m/E = \sin(a) = 2 \sin(a/2)\cos(a/2) \quad \text{i.e. the (1,1) matrix term of (3)}$$

$$\sin(a/2) = C \exp(-U(r)/2T) \sqrt{1 + dU/dr \, b/T} \quad \text{and} \quad \cos(a/2) = C \exp(-U(r)/2T) \sqrt{1+dU/dr \, b/T}$$

$$\text{Where } C = \sqrt{\exp(-U(r+b)/T) + \exp(-U(r-b)/T)}$$

Now $\sqrt{1 + dU/dr \, b/T} \sqrt{1+dU/dr \, b/T}$ is of the form $\sqrt{1-w^2}$ where w is the constraint and:

$$E = m/[2 \exp(-U(r)/T) \sqrt{1-w^2}]$$

In addition, we wish to point out that an energy difference (namely the potential difference) in moving from $r-b$ to $r+b$ causes a difference in pressure as well as density proportional to the energy difference $b dU/dr$.

Case of a Gas with No Potential

This case is somewhat more vague. In order to consider infinitesimals, one can take the density at an energy $e+de$ and one at $e-de$. The two square root probability densities are proportional to:

$\exp(-e/T)$ and $\exp(-(e+de)/T)$. It is not clear what the constraint equation should be. There does not seem to be an immediate force balance equation as in the case of the potential field. One may still consider (3) and note that

$$[\cos(a/2)^2 - \sin(a/2)^2] \cos(a/2) - 2 \cos(a/2)\sin(a/2) \sin(a/2) = \cos(a/2)$$

holds with the term in square brackets being proportional to the difference of partial pressures of the particles with energies $e-de$ and $e+de$. One can again divide by $\cos(a/2)$ and keep infinitesimal terms:

$$[\text{Difference in Partial pressures}]/[T N/\text{Vol}] = 2 \exp(-e/T) 2de/T \quad (5)$$

Thus, there is again a constraint equation relating pressure differences to a difference in energies. The factor $\exp(-e/T)$ shows the pressure differences change as one changes e . One can set the RHS to w and again obtain an analogous kinetic energy term $.5mw^2$ where M is proportional to $\exp(-e/T)$. Thus, as one moves from high energies e to lower ones, the analogous kinetic energy varies as $\exp(-e/T) vdv$ where v is the velocity.

Zitterbewegung and Constraints

In the 2×2 matrix system (2), it was found in [2]-[9] that zitterbewegung existed for the constraint matrix V which represented the velocity operator. The basic approach to zitterbewegung [1] seems to be calculating the time dependence of various operators using:

$$V(t) = \exp(iHt) V \exp(-iHt)$$

In the 2×2 matrix case, the matrices of (2) and (3) have the property that $H^*H = E I$ where I is the identity matrix. Thus, $\exp(iHt) = \cos(Et) + i \sin(Et) H$ demonstrating periodicity. It can also be seen that the magnitude of H is important (i.e., one needs (2), (3) does not have enough information).

If the statistical mechanical problems discussed above can be expressed within the framework of the 2x2 matrix model, it might be possible to apply zitterbewegung to a relevant constraint matrix as in [22] [24]. This in turn may predict physical periodic disturbances within the statistical mechanical system. It is already known from statistical mechanics that there are fluctuations in such systems, but physical oscillations may actually be related to creating the statistical mechanical space or energy density distributions. For example, there is a space density distribution in a gas with a potential which leads to pressure differences which counterbalance the force created by the potential. Zitterbewegung may suggest that oscillations in fact drive the density difference..

Case of a Gas with a Potential

This case has been described in [24], but without a magnitude for H, the “energy type” 2x2 matrix. In analogy with the regular 2x2 case, we can identify a constraint which is part of the 2x2 matrix and so also the energy using $E = m / \sqrt{1 - \text{constraint}^2}$ with $m = N/\text{Vol} \exp(-U(r)/T)/C1$ where C1 is a normalization constant. To carry out the analogy with the 2x2 case, a constraint of the form (4) can be used by dividing by T assuming the ideal gas law Pressure = density T.

The constraint is: $2 \exp(-U(r)/T) (-b dU/dr)$ (6) so $f1 - f2 = \text{constraint}$.

Then, one can obtain a number for $E = N/\text{Vol} \exp(-U(r)/T)/\sqrt{1 - \text{constraint}^2}$ to use as the frequency in zitterbewegung calculations.

This approach was not applied to the regular Dirac electron 2x2 matrix model. It does suggest, however, that momentum in the case of the moving electron may be related to a difference in pressures due to the “photon” bouncing back and forth in analogy with the pressure differences in the statistical mechanical models.

It should be noted that the constraint for the gas in a potential is of the identical form as that of the regular 2x2 matrix model and is also part of the form of the analogous energy matrix (2) (3). Thus, the model of motion of an electron is of the same math form as a tiny box of gas supported by differences in pressure.

Case of Gas with No Potential

For the consideration of the densities of gas particles with energies $e+de$ and $e-de$, we have applied the 2x2 matrix model and have seen that there is also a constraint matrix of the same form of that the regular 2x2 matrix system, i.e. a moving electron. Here we use the constraint (5) which applying the ideal gas law gives:

$F1 - f2 = 2 \exp(-e/T) 2de/T = w$ where w denotes the constraint.

Where f1 and f2 are the densities for $e+de$ and $e-de$. The analogous energy is again:

$$E = m / \sqrt{1-w^2} \quad \text{with } m/E = \sin(a) = 2 \exp(-e/T) / \sqrt{[\exp(-(e+de)/T) + \exp(-(e-de)/T)]}$$

Again, it might be possible to set $m = N/Vol \exp(-e/T)$.

Conclusion

If the above calculations are meaningful, it seems that one can perform zitterbewegung calculations for infinitesimal cases in a statistical gas, both with and without a potential. It is already known that there are fluctuations in a gas, but zitterbewegung would seem to imply that there are periodic oscillations. On average one would see “equilibrium” results, but there would be periodic fluctuations. Furthermore, these periodic oscillations might account for equilibrium properties such as pressure difference which balance such things as the force at a point in a gas with a potential. For the gas without a potential, the oscillations may be responsible for the partial pressure difference between particles with slightly different energies.

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